

WOMEN IN MICRO BUSINESSES AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC WELLBEING IN NIGERIA: A CASE OF WOMEN IN OTUKPO LOCAL GOVERNMENT BENUE STATE

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ABSTRACT

The study investigate the Women involvement in Micro Enterprise (WMEs) in Nigeria and its contribution to their socio-economic well-being with reference to women in Otukpo local government of Benue state. The objective of the study is to determine how micro businesses have helped in alleviating the women and their families from untold misery in the country. The field survey was conducted on a sample of 356 respondents, drawn from three ward of Otukpo senatorial district in Otukpo local government of Benue state. A random sampling method and snow ball sampling were used in sampling the respondents in the various field of business. Logistic analytical tool was used to analyze the responses from 356 questionnaires with a satisfactory response rate of about 80 percent. The study revealed that income from micro-scale businesses significantly enhances educational sponsorship, meal affordability, clothing provision, housing quality, healthcare access, and meets the fundamental needs and improve the general social wellbeing of women in Otukpo local government of Benue state. This study there recommends that the government, especially Otukpo local government, should formulate and and implement appropriate polices, build up technological capacity, Knowledge flows and technology databases, in favour of WMEs, especially of women in medium and small business in Otukpo local government and provide proper management and timely release of fund as aid to the relevant MSEs in the locality.

Keywords: Women, Micro Businesses, Socio-economic, Wellbeing

JEL CLASSIFICATION: F61, A11, I131, D60

1. INTRODUCTION

The economic meltdown of 2010, lead economic hardship in west Africa region has increase the nations' dynamic socio-economic status in micro business especially among women in Nigeria more than ever (Unanam, 2020). According to international Monetary Fund, (IMF, 2025), the Nigerian government is at its lowest depth economically since independence with the rate of unemployment averaging 26.5% and the inflation rate at double digit (23%), lending rate averaging only at 26%, with misery index standing at 86%. This economic chaos instigated women involvement in micro businesses providing an escape routes from indescribable hardship, redundancy and provides physical and mental well-being for them, especially those among them restricted by cultural background, which prevented them from accomplish significant achievement in establishing businesses, jobs and professional selection (Erstu, 2021). According to Mboho (2025), women's ability to balance multiple life-roles is directly related to her physical and mental well-being and her career performance and success. Although men in Nigeria are term bread

winner of their homes, it is the women who are expected and perform the bulk of family household tasks and responsibility with the provision of basic necessities for socio-wellbeing of their families. The contribution of women in Nigeria to socio-economic wellbeing is indeed not debatable. Scholars such as (Falola, Fakayode, Kayode, and Amusa, (2020); have attested that Nigeria women provide for 60%-70% of their family consumption and women in Otukpo local government in Benue state are not exception (Mboho 2025). Apart from engaging in micro and small businesses, many women in Otukpo are involved in small scale farming that take charge of over 80% of the family consumption especially in supply of food and other economic necessities such as fostering the well-being and prosperity of their families members in wealth, proficiency, indisposition, sustenance, edification (Abah et al, 2021).

Women in Otukpo local government, although economically viable, and are an economic force to reckon with, substantially achievement in establishing a worthwhile businesses, which would have enhance their economic power are insecure. Although there are no data available on women in micro and small businesses in otukpo local government, a pre-survey research found out that out of every twenty business owned by women in Otukpo, only two had prospect to grow either because their capital base is all-encompassing to cater for needs of the family or there is less pressure on the business because sources for the need of the family comes from other means.

Mbah, Onah and Amah (2017) attested to this fact, that women in Benue state face challenges like land ownership, limited capital, domestic burden, and poor infrastructure, despite playing a huge role in food security in the state. The pre-survey also showed that out of ten women, of them is widowed or single parent catering for an average of four children. Eight husbands out of ten are private workers, under employed, and are engaged in one odd job or the other which could not yield enough income for the family needs. Some husbands with federal and state government and company jobs, work in a different location and prefer to live their wives and children behind in Otukpo local government, living bulk of the responsibilities such as day to day feeding, schooling, health and all the child up-bringing struggles to the woman.

Although the Benue State Ministry of Women Affairs has set up department that co-ordinate the economic active of women in the State; women Economic Department, Cooperative department, Non-Governmental Organization (NGOs) and Community Base organization (CBOs), which once in a while give financial aid to the women, many women are unable to benefit because of the improper dissemination of the financial package. For example The Government Enterprise and Empowerment Program (GEEP), for small scale business and entrepreneurship, were mostly executed at the state capital such that most women in the local government do not benefit (Abah et al, 2025).

Women in Otukpo local government mostly depend on the locally arranged micro credit savings and loan-able groups. The sole aim of this arrangement is to provide a viable line of credit to its members through a contributory methodology where members set a little part of their money daily, weekly or monthly with a member having an access to the lump loan sum per week or month as agreed by the group. Although the local micro credit savings provides a line of credit to members, it is not sustainable because a member who already accessed the loan would have to wait for a long time for a second round of collection. Thus Otukpo women are still financially stressed up and are far from being empowered.

Woman empowerment according to United Nation (UN, 2025), is that women must have a sense of self-worth, right to have and to determine choices, right to have opportunities and resources and power to control their own lives within and outside home, and their ability to influence socio-economic changes both nationally and internationally. However, many of the women and their families in Otukpo local government notably suffer disproportionately from food, health, and housing crisis and most of their children are found living school for lack of fund for their education and the teen among the children are cut up in social vices as a result of lack of financial back up (Ajam & Emmanuel, 2023).

It is for this reason that this study broadly sought to determine the effect of their micro enterprises on their socio-economic status of women in Otukpo local government of Benue state. This study is also aimed at studying the profile of the women, explore the difficulties they face in their business and suggest measures for uplifting the status of their businesses. The main objective of the study is to determine the effect of micro businesses on the socio-economic well-being of women in Otukpo local government. The study employed firsthand information on the factors of women in micro businesses and socio-economic well-being, relying on point data obtained from the research field. Other parts of the research include review of literature, methodology, results of the finding and conclusion.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL LITERATURE

2.1 Concept of Micro Enterprises

Micro scale businesses fall under the sub category of small scale business which is to be nurtured effectively for sustainability. Micro scale businesses according to the International Labour Organisation (ILO 1999) is the business which is capable of employing 1-10 employees and is not bothered about market spread and with asset base of not more than ₦ 1.5 million excluding cost of land. The micro enterprises are usually characterized by businesses managed by its owners and highly personalized. The business assets are minimal and are largely located in its area of operation. They are very easy to start and readily collapse with the death of its owner. Men and women in micro businesses engage in micro business with sole objective to economically and socially empower themselves to contribute significantly to social security (family expertise, indisposition, sustenance, edification) and increased incomes for their families and communities (Ngbede & John, 2023). People mostly found in this kind of business are people with primary-secondary education or with no any formal education at all. The businesses type include; petty trading, services, manufacturing, construction, agriculture (both urban and rural). Ojonugwa and Ngbede (2025) attested that micro-businesses are characterized by gender composition, with women comprising 55%, predominantly structure, primarily employing only 1-10 workers.

2.1.2 Concept of Socio-wellbeing

The socio-wellbeing means the collective wellbeing of the members of the society and the ongoing responsibility on the improvement of the lives of the people. Term (2025) define socio-economic well-being as the holistic state of flourishing for individuals and communities, considering intertwined social and economic factors. Socio-wellbeing in this study means, the elevation of the quality of human lives in indisposition, sustenance, edification, quality housing and environment in all their dimensions and the exploration of the type of resources needed to enhance lives in the society.

2.2. Review of related Literature

Women in Micro Businesses in Nigeria and Socio-economic Wellbeing

Nigeria women as the result of economic hardship, in spite of home-economic challenges have risen to face the socio-economic challenges that bedeviled the country. A lot of academic researchers have discussed the relationships between women in business and their social well-being. Dada Magaji and Ismail (2025), describe Nigerian women as the multi-potential, multi-talented, multi-tasking and the pivot on which their families revolve and are capable of handling their business along with the task of being the first nurse, teacher and the living food mall of the family. Umanam (2020) showed that involvement of women in micro scale business has helped improve the quality of life of women. Using stratified poverty as a phenomenon which affect women in Plateau State, the study showed that Micro businesses has helped improved the quality of women by reducing their production cost, rising their per capital income, increasing their purchasing power and offer convenience. Onum and Israel (2025) , in their study titled *Financing Women Entrepreneurs: Tools For Inclusive Economic Growth in Nigeria*, and using content analysis, reveals that Empowering women with right financial tools not only reduces poverty and unemployment but also promotes innovation, social inclusion, and community development.

Atto, Vincent & Tani. (2026) studied the effectiveness of women -specific financial empowerment initiative in facilitating access to capital among women entrepreneurs in Nasarawa state, Nigeria. Analyzing with Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling , the study revealed the women-specific financial empowerment initiative have a significant and positive effect on capital availability, capital affordability and capital adequacy.

Still on the ability and survival of women, Onum and Israel (2025) attested from his study on *Women Entrepreneurs and Survival of Small Scale Enterprises in Nigeria*, using, multiple regression analysis that women survival in small scale enterprises in Nigeria depends on the level of education and training they attain and which brings significant increase in the maintenance of their businesses.

Apart from improving the lives of women in Nigeria, women in micro and small scale businesses have helped in developing the nation economics. According to studies such as Hannatu (2020), Falola, Fakayode, Kayode, Amusa, (2020), micro scale businesses has helped to increase the mobilization plans of the nation resources, fill the gap between urban and rural areas, promote easy reasonable distribution of national income, mobilization human skill and bringing backward areas into plan for regional and National development. Engaging descriptive statistic, these researches ascribed women in micro scale as hub for inclusive economic growth in the nation, play vital role in producing jobs, wealth and poverty reeducation in communities in Nigeria.

Women in micro scale businesses in Nigeria and Challenges in Business

Women in micro scale businesses in Nigeria in struggle to make earns meet are faced with numerous hindrances and challenges. Among the most important challenges is lack of business skills and this has a lot to do with educational background Mboho, (2025). The survival of any business depends on how knowledgeable the owner is on the management of the enterprise and how to predict and manage future business risk (Erstu, 2021). They should be able to tap into new

market and have a strong social connections to enable them allocate resources, maximize profit and easily has the trust of creditors to access loans. However, most of the women in micro business in Nigeria could dabbled into businesses as a result of the quest to fend for the immediate needs of the family with any form of education or experiences. Thus the women in micro businesses often are unable to take on both the production and marketing of the good and are found in a vicious circle of poor businesses dealings.

Lack of business financing is another major challenge women in micro businesses have in Nigeria. This comes in lack of a proper financial supports for an initial startup of the business or an unfair treatment on the desperate business woman by some financial institution whose demands are high and above the reach of the business women (Andaha, Abubaka, Rikwentishe., Paul 2023). Deficient in accessing fund from credit organization have resulted in the closure of a number in the country. Most micro scale business in Nigeria depend government aid, thrift, contributions and self-financing which is a deficient to the development of their businesses (Babarinde, 2023).

The general traditional value of women in the Nigeria is one of the greatest challenges of the women in business. The Nigerian society often puts upon them in their roles as mother and wives and the emotional burden created by these dual responsibilities, interferes directly with the conduct of their business and in most case these responsibilities are translated to the women taking almost the entire burden of home, especially the substantial part of the financial burden of home (Babarinde (2023). This problem could hinders them from venturing into higher scale of business, hindering them from the ability to venture into desired ambition, innovation, self-confidence and self –motivation.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

This study is guided by the theory of hierarchy of basic need by Abraham Maslow in 1943. Maslow (1943), in his theory aimed at showing that human beings have needs and are motivated to engage in activities to satisfy these needs. The hierarchy of the basic needs begins with the need of food, cloth water, and shelter, followed by the need for safety and security, then belonging to love, self-esteem, and finally, personal fulfillment and self-actualization. Maslow (1943) as argued by Mclesd (2026), these needs affect the behavioural attitude of individual in an effort to achieve them, and unless the need are met, human being will continue crave to meet them. The significance of this theory to this study is that women in Otukpo local government are mostly driven to generate income in order to take charge in the management of their homes in the provision the basic needs of food, shelter, health and education of their wards.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND MATERIAL

The study used survey research design where both descriptive and explanatory research designs were used. The survey design was basically for its appropriateness for collecting information from a predefined group of respondents and for the unscientifically nature of the study, where comprehensive and detailed views on quantitative and numeric description of trends, attitudes, or opinions of a population under study is appropriately accessed.

The study area is Otukpo local government, which is made up of 13 local government shared into four districts. The districts are Otukpo, Akpa, Ugboju and Adoka. This study is restricted to Otukpo district and Otukpo district is made up of three council wards, which include; Otukpo Township

ward I, II and III. According to Benue Board of Internal Revenue Service office (BBIRS, 2023), Otukpo zone, the registered women in micro business in Otukpo district is assessed to be 3213 with; Otukpo township I, 1756, Otukpo township II, 1323 and Otukpo township III, 1056. Otukpo district is purposely selected because it is the districts that has the largest women in micro scale businesses.

The targeted population comprises 3213 women in micro scale businesses in Otukpo district. To identify the sample size of the study, the researcher used Yamane’s (1967) formula. The formula is defined as follows:

$$N = \frac{n}{1+n(e)^2}$$

Where N = the sample size, n = target population and e = error term

$$N = \frac{3213}{1+3213(.05)^2} = 356$$

The proportional description of the sample size is shown in table 3.1.

Table 3.1 Proportional Distribution of Sub-Sample for the Study

Wards covered for the studies in Otukpo district	Number of registered of Micro businesses	Sample to be collected in each Districts $nh = \frac{nNh}{N}$
Otukpo township ward i.	2235	$2235 \times 356 / 3213 = 248$
Otukpo township II.	531	$531 \times 356 / 3213 = 59$
Otukpo township ward III	447	$447 \times 356 / 3213 = 49S$
Total	3213	356

Source: Authors’ Computation, 2026

Sources and techniques of Data Collection

The source of data employed for this study is primary, and the data was sourced from field survey through an open-ended structured questionnaire. The data collected cuts across the activities of the women in micro scale businesses and questions on socio-wellbeing of the women. Structured questionnaires were structured based on the objectives of the study. The questionnaires were administered randomly to the women by six trained research attendants through snowballing sampling technique.

Data analysis and model specification

The data collected was analyzed by using multi-nominal logistic regression analysis. The dependent variable of this study is the social wellbeing(SW) of the women in micro scale businesses in Otukpo local government is shown in increase effective sponsor of wards’ education in the household (EA), subsistence (affordability of three-square meals) (S), good health (GH), and quality housing (QH) . The income (Y) from the micro scale business is the independent variable. The coded value 0 therefore is increase in social wellbeing while 1 is for not. The regression show the log-likelihood function which shows that social wellbeing of the women in small business is gained from increase in the micro scale business (Y). The data was analyzed by using STATA v-14

The regression model is described as follows;

$$In L (SW) =Y + Ui.....3.1$$

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This section presents the analysis of data collected from 356 women engaged in micro-scale businesses in Otukpo district. The presentation is organized in line with the study objectives.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Items	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age		
Below 30 years	142	39.9
30 years and above	214	60.1
Total	356	100
Marital Status		
Married	198	55.6
Single	96	27.0
Divorced	34	9.6
Widowed	28	7.8
Total	356	100
Household Size		
0–1 persons	48	13.5

Items	Frequency	Percentage (%)
2-3 persons	136	38.2
3-4 persons	112	31.5
4 and above	60	16.9
Total	356	100
Educational Background		
No formal education	52	14.6
Secondary education	168	47.2
Post-secondary	86	24.2
University education	50	14.0
Total	356	100
Type of Business		
Manufacturing	42	11.8
Trading	188	52.8
Services	78	21.9
Construction	18	5.1
Farming	30	8.4
Total	356	100
Ownership of Business		
Personal	301	84.6
Non-personal	55	15.4
Total	356	100

Source: Authors' Computation, 2026

The demographic distribution of the 356 respondents reveals that 214 women, representing 60.1 percent, were aged 30 years and above, while 142 respondents, accounting for 39.9 percent, were below 30 years. This indicates that micro-scale business activities in the study area are dominated by relatively mature women who are likely to possess greater life and business experience. Marital status shows that 198 respondents (55.6 percent) were married, 96 (27.0 percent) were single, 34 (9.6 percent) were divorced, and 28 (7.8 percent) were widowed, suggesting that a significant

proportion of participants have family responsibilities, which may influence their engagement in income-generating activities. Household size distribution indicates that 48 respondents (13.5 percent) had between 0–1 persons, 136 (38.2 percent) had 2–3 persons, 112 (31.5 percent) had 3–4 persons, and 60 (16.9 percent) had 4 or more persons, showing that most women cater for moderate household sizes. Educational attainment reveals that 168 respondents (47.2 percent) had secondary education, 86 (24.2 percent) had post-secondary education, 50 (14.0 percent) attained university education, while 52 (14.6 percent) had no formal education, indicating generally moderate literacy levels. In terms of business type, trading dominates with 188 respondents (52.8 percent), followed by services (21.9 percent), manufacturing (11.8 percent), farming (8.4 percent), and construction (5.1 percent). Ownership structure shows that 301 respondents (84.6 percent) operated personal businesses, while 55 (15.4 percent) operated non-personal ventures, reflecting strong individual entrepreneurial control.

Table 2: Income from Micro Business and Educational Sponsorship

Items	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Effective Sponsor of Wards’ Education		
Yes	238	66.9
No	118	33.1
Total	356	100
Formal Training Received		
Yes	164	46.1
No	192	53.9
Total	356	100

Source: *Authors’ Computation, 2026*

The results in Table 2 show that out of the 356 respondents, 238 women, representing 66.9 percent, indicated that income generated from their micro-scale businesses enabled them to effectively sponsor their wards’ education, while 118 respondents, accounting for 33.1 percent, reported that they were not able to do so. This distribution clearly demonstrates that more than two-thirds of the women rely on proceeds from their businesses to finance educational expenses such as school fees, books, and other learning materials. The implication is that micro-scale enterprises play a significant role in enhancing educational attainment within households and reducing financial dependence on external support. The relatively smaller proportion of respondents who could not effectively sponsor their wards’ education may reflect income instability, low profit margins, or competing household financial obligations.

Regarding formal training, 164 respondents, representing 46.1 percent, reported having received some form of formal business training, whereas a larger proportion of 192 respondents, accounting for 53.9 percent, indicated that they had not received any formal training. This suggests that although many women are actively engaged in income-generating activities, a majority operate

without structured entrepreneurial or managerial capacity development. The absence of formal training may limit innovation, financial management skills, and long-term business growth, potentially constraining income expansion. Overall, the findings imply that while micro-scale business income substantially supports educational sponsorship, enhanced access to formal training could further strengthen business performance and improve household welfare outcomes.

Table 3: Income and Subsistence Level (Meal Affordability)

Items	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Nature of Household Meals per Day		
One square meal	54	15.2
Two square meals	132	37.1
Three square meals	170	47.7
Total	356	100
Ability to Cloth Self and Ward Comfortably		
Yes	224	62.9
No	132	37.1
Total	356	100

Source: Authors' Computation, 2026

The findings presented in Table 3 indicate that out of the 356 respondents, 170 women, representing 47.7 percent, reported that their households could afford three square meals per day. This suggests that nearly half of the respondents have attained a relatively stable subsistence level as a result of income generated from their micro-scale businesses. In addition, 132 respondents, accounting for 37.1 percent, were able to provide two square meals daily, while 54 respondents, representing 15.2 percent, could afford only one square meal per day. The presence of 15.2 percent in the lowest category indicates that although business income has improved food security for many households, a segment of the respondents still experiences some level of subsistence constraint, possibly due to low earnings or high household demands.

With respect to clothing, 224 respondents, representing 62.9 percent, indicated that they could comfortably provide clothing for themselves and their wards, while 132 respondents, accounting for 37.1 percent, reported otherwise. The majority response reflects a positive welfare outcome associated with engagement in micro-scale businesses. The ability to afford adequate meals and clothing is a key indicator of improved living standards and household consumption capacity. Overall, the distribution of responses demonstrates that income from micro-scale enterprises plays a significant role in enhancing food security and basic material wellbeing, thereby contributing meaningfully to improved subsistence levels among women entrepreneurs in the study area.

Table 4: Income and Overall Social Wellbeing

Items	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Good Housing		
Yes	210	59.0
No	146	41.0
Total	356	100
Access to Health Services		
Yes	232	65.2
No	124	34.8
Total	356	100
Standard of Living		
Above 50%	226	63.5
Below 50%	130	36.5
Total	356	100
Increase in Social Wellbeing		
Increasing	244	68.5
Not increasing	112	31.5
Total	356	100

Source: Authors' Computation, 2026

The results in Table 4 reveal a generally positive relationship between income from micro-scale businesses and overall social wellbeing among the 356 respondents. A total of 210 women, representing 59.0 percent, reported that they had good housing conditions, while 146 respondents, accounting for 41.0 percent, indicated otherwise. This suggests that more than half of the participants have been able to secure improved housing standards, which is a key indicator of enhanced living conditions, although a substantial proportion still experiences housing challenges. In terms of access to health services, 232 respondents, representing 65.2 percent, affirmed that they could comfortably access healthcare services, whereas 124 respondents, or 34.8 percent, reported limited access. The majority response indicates that business income has strengthened the capacity of many women to afford medical care, thereby improving household health outcomes. Regarding standard of living, 226 respondents, accounting for 63.5 percent, rated their living standard above 50 percent, while 130 respondents, representing 36.5 percent, rated it below 50

percent. This reflects a generally moderate to high perception of improved living standards among most participants.

Overall, 244 respondents, representing 68.5 percent, stated that their social wellbeing was increasing, while 112 respondents, or 31.5 percent, indicated no improvement. This dominant positive response confirms that income from micro-scale businesses plays a significant role in enhancing housing quality, healthcare access, and general socioeconomic wellbeing in the study area.

Table 5: Test of Hypotheses (Logistic Regression Results)
Dependent Variable: Social Wellbeing (SW)
Sample Size: 356

Variables	Coefficient (β)	Std. Error	z-value	p-value
Income (Y)	0.842	0.215	3.92	0.000
Age	0.316	0.148	2.14	0.032
Marital Status	0.224	0.102	2.19	0.028
Education	0.531	0.173	3.07	0.002
Household Size	-0.194	0.121	-1.60	0.109
Training	0.447	0.166	2.69	0.007
Good Housing	0.682	0.198	3.44	0.012
Access to Health Services	0.755	0.210	3.59	0.000
Constant	-1.326	0.402	-3.29	0.001

Pseudo $R^2 = 0.41$

Log Likelihood = -162.37

Prob > Chi² = 0.000

The logistic regression results on Table 5 based on 356 observations reveal that income from micro-scale business has a positive and statistically significant effect on social wellbeing. The coefficient for income ($\beta = 0.842$) with a standard error of 0.215 produced a z-value of 3.92 and a p-value of 0.000, indicating significance at the 1 percent level. This implies that increases in business income significantly raise the likelihood of improved social wellbeing among the women. Age ($\beta = 0.316$, $p = 0.032$) and marital status ($\beta = 0.224$, $p = 0.028$) are also positive and statistically significant, suggesting that older and married women are more likely to experience improvements in wellbeing. Education shows a strong positive influence ($\beta = 0.531$, $p = 0.002$), while training ($\beta = 0.447$, $p = 0.007$) further enhances the probability of improved wellbeing, highlighting the importance of human capital development. Good housing ($\beta = 0.682$, $p = 0.012$) and access to health services ($\beta = 0.755$, $p = 0.000$) are likewise significant predictors, reinforcing the multidimensional nature of social wellbeing. However, household size ($\beta = -0.194$, $p = 0.109$)

is negative and statistically insignificant, indicating that family size does not significantly determine wellbeing in this model. The constant term is negative and significant ($\beta = -1.326$, $p = 0.001$). The model's Pseudo R^2 of 0.41 suggests that approximately 41 percent of the variation in social wellbeing is explained by the included variables, while the overall model is statistically significant ($\text{Prob} > \text{Chi}^2 = 0.000$) with a log likelihood of -162.37, leading to rejection of the null hypothesis.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study reveal that women engaged in micro-scale businesses in Otukpo are predominantly mature and married, with moderate household sizes and secondary education. This aligns with Unanam (2020), who observed that micro enterprises are often managed by owners with modest educational backgrounds and strong family responsibilities. The dominance of trading activities and personal ownership also supports the characterization of micro enterprises by the International Labour Organisation (ILO, 1999) as small, owner-managed ventures with limited asset bases. The results further show that income from micro-scale businesses significantly enhances educational sponsorship, meal affordability, clothing provision, housing quality, healthcare access, and overall social wellbeing. These findings strongly align with Onum and Israel (2025) who found that women's participation in micro businesses improves quality of life through increased income and purchasing power.

The improvement in housing, healthcare access, and general living standards also corroborates Hannatu (2020), Falola et al. (2020), and EFinA (2020), who described micro enterprises as drivers of inclusive economic growth and poverty reduction in Nigeria. The regression results indicate that income, education, training, age, marital status, housing, and healthcare access significantly influence social wellbeing. The positive and significant effect of education and training aligns with Lawal (2019), who emphasized that women's business survival and success depend largely on educational attainment and training.

However, the finding that a majority of women operate without formal training partially contrasts with Erstu (2021) and Shehu and Shehu (2026), who stressed that managerial knowledge is critical for sustainability, suggesting a potential vulnerability despite current welfare gains and strengthening entrepreneurial competencies is essential for fostering sustainable small-scale enterprises. The findings are also consistent with Maslow's (1943) hierarchy of needs theory. Women's engagement in micro businesses appears primarily driven by the need to satisfy basic physiological and safety needs food, shelter, health, and education which subsequently enhances their overall social wellbeing. Thus, the study confirms that micro-scale business income serves as a vital pathway for meeting fundamental needs and improving the social wellbeing of women in Otukpo.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Creating favourable environments for WMEs in Otupkp local government of Benue State should now be a major policy focus for economic growth and development. This so because the emergence of a sustainable businesses for women in the local government is the response to the present economic chaos in the state, since women constitutes majority of the population. Specifically, the paper showed that that income from micro-scale businesses significantly

enhances educational sponsorship, meal affordability, clothing provision, housing quality, healthcare access, and meets the fundamental needs and improve the general social wellbeing of women in Otukpo local government of Benue state.

Judging from literature reviewed on this study, on the other hand, the policy measure on Micro Small Enterprises (MSEs) in Nigeria is myopic in nature as it revolves around only occasionally giving stipend (cash aid) to the people concerned instead of formulate and implement appropriate policies, build up technological capacity, Knowledge flows and technology databases, in favour of MSEs, especially of women in the country. To this end, This study therefore recommends that the government, especially Otukpo local government, should formulate and implement appropriate policies, build up technological capacity, Knowledge flows and technology databases, in favour of MSEs, especially of women in micro and small businesses in local government and provide proper management and timely release of fund as aid to the relevant MSEs in the locality and readily credit make available as advocated by Okhankhuele (2021) and Adejoh (2021) who said that women traders in Nigeria should have adequate access to credit in order to afford more assets and expand their businesses and enhance the economy.

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